

The decline of soft power: Narratives beyond Nye

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Abstract

This paper argues that the concept of soft power, as originally formulated by Joseph Nye, is no longer fully applicable in today's context, given both the nature of the values it promotes and the evolving means by which these values are disseminated, as well as the actors who communicate them. Using a problematization approach, the paper shows that the Western values described by Nye in 1990 were once highly attractive to countries that lacked them—particularly in Eastern Europe. Today, however, many of these countries have already adopted these values, diminishing the relative attractiveness of soft power. The paper concludes that in networked societies—characterised by declining message credibility, the erosion of core values, and nearly five billion individuals interacting in a platformed world—narratives and strategic alliances operate in a radically different environment, far removed from the context in which soft power once flourished.

Keywords: soft power, public diplomacy, the power of narratives, global communication, non-state actors

1. Introduction

The concept of soft power, introduced by Joseph Nye in 1990 and further developed in 2004, is defined as the ability to achieve desired goals through attraction rather than coercion or payments. According to Nye (1990, 2004), a country can implement foreign policy effectively if it possesses values that other nations find attractive. The main sources of this power are a country's culture, values, policies, and moral legitimacy, which generate influence without recourse to coercion or material incentives (Nye, 2004; 2019).

During the first two decades of the 21st century, soft power gradually became a buzzword in studies of international communication, public diplomacy, and international influence. It has been widely used to describe various forms of attractiveness and symbolic influence, often without sufficient conceptual clarity or methodological rigour (Fan, 2007; Mattern, 2005; Rothman, 2011; Gilboa, 2008; Bakalov, 2019; Saliu, 2023). A critical analysis, however, reveals that soft power contains clear weaknesses and gaps, particularly in the contemporary global context.

First, the attractiveness of soft power values has been devalued. When Nye coined the concept at the end of the Cold War, he assumed that countries from the socialist Eastern European bloc would be drawn to Western values. Accordingly, democracy, human rights, sound policies, and a morally grounded foreign policy were identified as key sources of soft power. Today, many states, including those in Eastern Europe, have adopted these values, reducing the gap that once generated international admiration

(Zhang & Wu, 2019; Winkler, 2019). As Hagström and Gustafsson (2019) observe, “we live in a time when people are more aware of the power of narratives in international politics” (p. 387), suggesting that a country’s ability to attract admiration can no longer be taken for granted.

Second, the technological revolution and global networking have fragmented the influence of soft power. Beyond states, numerous non-state actors—including individuals, companies, non-governmental organisations, and other groups—now disseminate narratives and values through digital platforms (Castells, 2009; Marlin-Bennett, 2022). This widespread connectivity enables them to challenge state-sponsored messages and promote alternative narratives, thereby diminishing states’ control over international public perception. As Nye himself acknowledges in his 2019 work, “some non-state actors can effectively compete with the traditional soft power of states” (p. 1).

Third, soft power depends on a specific historical context and asymmetric value relations that no longer prevail. At the time of its formulation, a clear distinction existed between countries that possessed attractive values and those that did not. Today, these differences have largely diminished, and culture, political ideals, and morally framed foreign policies are no longer exclusive (Nye, 1990; Hagström & Gustafsson, 2019). This creates a theoretical gap, as soft power can no longer fully account for the dynamics of global influence.

Fourth, the measurement of soft power remains methodologically problematic. Soft power is very difficult to measure and quantify, and most studies focus on cataloguing resources rather than assessing their actual impact (Çevik, 2019; Roselle et al., 2014). This suggests that the concept lacks clear empirical tools for evaluating effectiveness.

Finally, shifting global perceptions have further undermined the relevance of soft power. In a context defined by decentralised information flows, states no longer maintain effective control over how their values are interpreted or disseminated, as individuals communicate directly and actively shape global narratives (Winkler, 2019; Saliu, 2022a). In this context, for soft power to be effective, it must be projected toward foreign publics rather than directed solely at government offices, and both state and non-state actors play a role in transmitting it through public diplomacy activities. Put differently, soft power is what states *have*, whereas public diplomacy is what states *do* to project and communicate these values. By conceptualizing soft power as a communicative process through which a country’s values are transmitted to foreign audiences, this paper adopts a perspective rooted in international communication, rather than in traditional international relations or conventional diplomacy.

This paper aims to examine the weaknesses and conceptual gaps of soft power, assessing whether this classical framework can adequately address the challenges of a globalised and digitalised world. It is guided by the following research question: How have contemporary communication dynamics reshaped the mechanisms and underlying assumptions of soft power? The study reviews the existing literature to identify the concept’s limitations in the contemporary context and, through a problematization approach, analyses key critiques, transformations in value systems, and the growing influence of modern narratives and non-state actors. Ultimately, the paper seeks to draw critical insights into the boundaries of the concept and to evaluate

the extent to which Nye's formulation remains applicable in an era of networked information and communication

2. Literature review

2.1. The meaning of soft power

The concept of soft power was developed by Joseph Nye in his 1990 study *Bound to Lead* and was later revised and expanded. In 2004, in his book *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics*, he gave the concept its full form. Nye (2004) defines soft power as the ability to achieve desired results through attraction rather than coercion. This type of power stems from a country's culture, values, policies, and moral legitimacy, creating a form of influence that is not imposed by force or money. According to Nye (1990, 2004, 2008, 2019, 2021), a country can implement foreign policy effectively if it possesses values that are attractive to other nations. Soft power is "the ability to get what you want through attraction rather than coercion or payments" (Nye, 2004, p. x). Soft power is not merely influence; it is influence that emerges from admiration and respect. A country may often obtain preferred outcomes in world politics because other countries choose to follow it, admiring its values, emulating its example, and aspiring to its level of prosperity and openness (Nye, 2004, 2019). The essence of Nye's concept of soft power lies in being attractive to others, rather than influencing or coercing them through hard power, such as economic or military means.

Soft power is not only a tool used by governments to win the hearts and minds of foreign publics; today, individuals play an increasingly significant role, as they are globally connected to one another. As Marlin-Bennett (2022) explains, "... soft power attracts through communication, that is, information flowing about a desirable situation, process, or relationship. The flow of information can be characterised by the properties of its content (what the message says), its velocity (direction and speed), and who has access to it (intentionally or unintentionally)" (p. 440).

A country's soft power is promoted through public diplomacy (Nye, 2019). Nye has also argued elsewhere that a country's soft power is advanced by public diplomacy (Barlas & Yanik, 2021). Public diplomacy was traditionally understood as addressing "the influence of public attitudes on the formation and execution of foreign policies" (Cull, 2006, p. 1). Gregory (2011) defines public diplomacy as "an instrument used by states, associations of states, and some sub-state and non-state actors to understand cultures, attitudes and behaviour; [to] build and manage relationships; influence thoughts and mobilise actions to advance their interests and values" (p. 353). According to Gilboa (2016), "public diplomacy is a communication process states, nonstate actors, and organisations employ to influence the policies of a foreign government by influencing its citizens" (p. 2). Such influence is further achieved through sustained efforts to inform and engage foreign publics. Similarly, Frederick (1993) describes its objective as "to influence a foreign government, by influencing its citizens" (p. 229). In this sense, soft power refers to what countries possess, while public diplomacy refers to what countries do. Public diplomacy is presented as an action or instrument, whereas soft power can be understood as a value or resource (Saliu, 2020, 2022a, 2023).

Soft power and public diplomacy are therefore closely interrelated concepts. Studies examining soft power and its manifestation through public diplomacy programs

suggest the need for an interdisciplinary approach to develop a more sustainable understanding of public diplomacy (Hayden, 2012). This field appears to be one of the most multidisciplinary areas in contemporary scholarship (Gilboa, 2008). Public diplomacy, which disseminates the values associated with soft power, continues to sit at the intersection of international relations and communication sciences. Some scholars situate public diplomacy primarily within the field of international relations and diplomacy (Nye, 2004; Melissen, 2005), while others approach it from the perspectives of communication and public relations (Ingenhoff et al., 2021; Di Martino, 2019; Gilboa, 2008; Cowan & Arsenault, 2008; Yun, 2009). An analysis of 2,124 articles on public diplomacy published between 1965 and 2017 found that most studies positioned public diplomacy as a tool of soft power within international relations, followed closely by research approaching it from communication and public relations perspectives (Sevin et al., 2019).

The relationship between soft power and public diplomacy is significant, as soft power can only be effective when it is communicated to foreign audiences through public diplomacy. Moreover, for soft power to have an effect, the values being promoted must be attractive at the time of their dissemination, meaning they must align with the prevailing context, and the actors conveying these values must be perceived as credible and trustworthy.

A central problem of soft power concerns its means and mechanisms (Rothman, 2011). In other words, what are the values of soft power, which Nye refers to as its sources? According to Nye (1990, 2004, 2008), these sources consist of: (a) a country's culture, when it is attractive to others; (b) its political ideals and good governance practices; and (c) a foreign policy grounded in moral authority. This attractiveness can be generated through the demonstration of soft power values to foreign publics, a process that transforms soft power into narrative power (Winkler, 2019). As Hagström and Gustafsson (2019) note, "We are living at a time when people appear to have become more aware of the power of narratives in international politics" (p. 387). Narrative power thus shifts the focus of soft power toward the fields of strategic communication and public relations, rather than traditional international relations.

In other words, it is necessary to present one's values to external audiences; however, in times of division, the question arises as to which values can be perceived as attractive. Nye addresses this issue by defining such values within the context of the Cold War.

2.2. Criticisms of soft power

Soft power has become one of the most frequently used terms in political and academic discourse, yet it is often applied superficially, approaching the status of a buzzword (Gilboa, 2008). During the first decades of the 21st century, the concept has been widely employed in studies on country image, branding, reputation, national values, diplomacy, international relations, and, more broadly, international public communication. Despite its extensive use, decades after Nye introduced the term, the empirical measurement of soft power and the critical examination of its theoretical foundations remain insufficient and highly necessary (Lee & Melissen, 2011). Over time, soft power has expanded to include almost any form of non-coercive influence, resulting in conceptual overstretch. As a consequence, the term has become analytically blurred, overloaded, and increasingly detached from clear theoretical

boundaries, often functioning more as a normative label than as a precise and operationalizable concept (Fan, 2007).

The popularity of soft power has contributed to its uncontrolled and uncritical usage, rendering it theoretically weak and discursively overused. This situation has prompted calls for practical and normative reformulations of the concept (Mattern, 2005). Other scholars argue that soft power has become a dominant label and an almost unavoidable reference point in the literature, frequently cited without sustained critical reflection on its limitations (Bakalov, 2019). This excessive reliance has led to what Rothman (2011) describes as analytical emptiness, where soft power operates more as a rhetorical slogan than as a rigorous theoretical instrument. Haugaard (2019) situates soft power within a broader debate on the conceptual inflation of power, observing that familiar terms are often reproduced due to academic fashion rather than analytical necessity.

Beyond conceptual inflation, soft power also faces persistent methodological challenges. Even many years after Nye coined the term, the empirical measurement of soft power and its systematic theoretical refinement remain pressing issues (Lee & Melissen, 2011). Measuring soft power is far from a neutral or straightforward scientific process (Zhang & Wu, 2019; Boulding, 1989; Jansson, 2025). As Çevik (2019) notes, “soft power is very difficult to both measure and quantify” (p. 55), because it is impossible to apply either qualitative or quantitative methods to fully assess its effects (Henne, 2022). Roselle et al. (2014) further argue that most analyses of soft power focus on identifying and categorizing assets or resources and on describing how these tools might be used, rather than examining whether, how, and under what conditions actual influence occurs.

Instead of assessing outcomes and effects, much of the literature has reduced soft power to a sophisticated cataloguing of instruments and resources, leaving its explanatory and empirical value largely unresolved.

3. Methodology

This paper employs the methodology of a problematizing review, an analytical and critical approach that seeks to challenge established assumptions and expand conventional ways of understanding a theoretical concept (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2020; Gossel, 2022). Unlike descriptive, systematic, or integrative review approaches, problematization does not aim to synthesise empirical findings or test hypotheses. Instead, it focuses on re-examining dominant understandings, identifying theoretical gaps, and assessing the conceptual limits of an existing paradigm (Weder, 2022; Foucault, 1988). This analytical approach is novel and has been successfully applied in management communication, organisational studies, and diplomacy; problematization is becoming increasingly common in marketing, applied management, communication studies, strategic communication, public relations, entrepreneurial communication, and related fields (Goyanes, 2020; Gossel, 2022; Alvesson & Sandberg, 2020; Chatterjee & Davison, 2021).

This methodology is particularly appropriate for the present study, as soft power is a concept formulated within a specific historical and normative context—the end of the Cold War—yet it continues to be widely used today, often without being reassessed in light of profound transformations in global communication, digital technologies, and

the pluralisation of international actors (Gossel, 2022; Nye, 1990, 2004, 2019). Problematization enables critical distancing from the naturalisation of the concept and from its treatment as a self-evident analytical category. Rather than building knowledge through the accumulation of findings, this methodology produces knowledge through the critical questioning and dismantling of the foundational assumptions underlying existing theories (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2011, 2020; Gossel, 2022). In this sense, problematization focuses on identifying unresolved tensions, conceptual contradictions, and methodological limitations, and on evaluating whether—and to what extent—a concept remains applicable under new social and communicative conditions (Bianco, 2018; Bowden & Kelly, 2018).

In this study, the problematization of the soft power literature is conducted through a critical examination of three main dimensions. First, it examines the fundamental values of the concept by analysing how culture, political ideals, good practices, and morally grounded foreign policy have been constructed as sources of attractiveness, and why these sources have lost their exclusivity in the contemporary global context (Zhang & Wu, 2019). Second, it analyses the mechanisms through which soft power operates, assessing their limitations in a decentralised communication environment in which non-state actors and networked individuals directly shape the circulation of narratives (Marlin-Bennett, 2022; Winkler, 2019). Third, it engages with related concepts—such as public diplomacy, narrative power, and digital communication—that challenge and relativise the classical understanding of attractiveness as a form of power.

A central element of this methodology is reflexivity. The research does not treat the literature as a neutral or objective body of knowledge, but as a product of specific historical, institutional, and value-based contexts (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2020; Weder et al., 2019). Within this framework, soft power is analysed not as a universal and stable concept, but as a theoretical construct shaped by particular historical circumstances and asymmetrical power relations. New empirical studies—that is, those not aligned with the nature of this study—have not been taken into account, as this is what the methodology prescribes.

Through problematization, this paper seeks to offer a more critical, nuanced, and contextual understanding of soft power. It highlights the theoretical and methodological weaknesses of the concept and explains why it can no longer function as a sufficient analytical framework in an era of digital communication and globally distributed narratives shaped by media and individuals. This reflexive engagement with the literature aims to identify the tensions, contradictions, and theoretical gaps that emerge when soft power is applied outside the historical context in which it was originally formulated. In this way, the literature is treated as an object of critical analysis rather than as a normative authority, enabling a deeper reassessment of the relevance of soft power in the age of networked communication.

4. Discussion

4.1. Towards a revised understanding of soft power

Building on the problematizing methodological approach, the critical analysis indicates that soft power has lost much of its classical exclusivity and effectiveness. Values that were once perceived as attractive by international audiences have become

widely diffused and are now interpreted through diverse cultural, historical, and political contexts (Zhang & Wu, 2019). In other words, in 1990, Nye emphasised (and later reiterated in 2004) that freedom, democracy, human rights, individual opportunities, quality education, and similar values are highly attractive to countries that do not possess them. Consequently, in seeking to achieve these values, countries follow one's policies without the need for threats or coercion. In this context, Nye was referring to the countries of the Eastern European bloc, which at that time lacked these values. Today, however, most of those countries are part of the EU and have achieved them.

Traditional mechanisms of soft power, such as managed media environments and state-controlled public diplomacy, face increasing challenges in a decentralised communication landscape, where individuals and non-state actors actively shape and circulate narratives (Marlin-Bennett, 2022; Winkler, 2019). Narrative power, storytelling, and digital media play a central role in shaping global perceptions, underscoring the sensitivity of soft power to framing, interpretation, and audience reception (Pamment, 2021; Crilley et al., 2020).

A critical reading of the literature reveals several contradictions and theoretical gaps. While the concept of soft power continues to be defended through the academic authority associated with Harvard and the intellectual prestige of Joseph Nye, it does not sufficiently account for the transformations in global communication or the growing influence of distributed and networked actors. In this context, soft power can no longer be treated as a comprehensive analytical framework, but rather as a fragile and relational construct, highly dependent on global narratives, perceptions, and media dynamics.

4.2. Weaknesses and gaps of soft power from a communicative perspective

Although soft power has been widely recognised as a form of non-military influence with global relevance, contemporary scholarship highlights several structural and communicative weaknesses that call into question its effectiveness and sustainability. One of the most frequently cited criticisms concerns conceptual ambiguity. Durrani (2023), echoing earlier critiques by Fan (2007), argues that soft power has expanded to encompass almost any form of non-military influence, thereby losing clear analytical boundaries and becoming a theoretically “fuzzy” concept. This conceptual inflation makes it difficult to distinguish between the sources of soft power, the communicative processes through which it operates, and its actual effects on audience behaviour (Rothman, 2011; Gallarotti, 2022a).

A direct consequence of this ambiguity is the methodological difficulty associated with measurement and evaluation. The impact of soft power remains hard to operationalise due to the absence of clear and standardised indicators. Many studies rely on narrative and semiotic analyses which, while providing interpretive depth, remain subjective and constrained by selective source sampling. An overreliance on Western media further risks producing partial perspectives, overlooking local and regional narratives that more directly shape public opinion (Durrani, 2023; Pamment, 2021).

Another significant gap in the literature concerns its near-exclusive focus on the accumulation of soft power, while largely neglecting processes of reputational loss and erosion. Durrani (2023) addresses this limitation through the concept of Negative Watch and the Negative Watch Index (NWI), which examine visual narratives and

recurring thematic patterns that can undermine an actor's international image. This perspective demonstrates that soft power is deeply sensitive to media dynamics, framing practices, and global storytelling processes (Pamment, 2021).

Narratives are transmitted through traditional media—text, sound, and visuals—and increasingly through digital and social platforms. Visual elements, including photographs, maps, public relations materials, popular culture imagery, and films, play a particularly influential role in shaping national images and foreign policy perceptions in the digital age (Crilley et al., 2020; van Noort, 2020; Bjola et al., 2019). Within this expansive online environment, narratives and storytelling lie at the core of national identity and international image formation, directly affecting global perceptions and reputational outcomes (Lepore, 2019; Saliu, 2022a). However, the values communicated to foreign audiences today—constructed and circulated through these diverse channels—differ substantially from those described by Nye at the end of the twentieth century.

From a communicative perspective, another critical shortcoming of soft power theory is its limited engagement with affective and emotional dimensions. Nye's framework focuses primarily on structural sources of attraction, yet emotions, sensitivities, and symbolic identification play a decisive role in how international audiences receive and interpret state messages (Haugaard, 2019). Soft power operates not only through institutions or cultural outputs, but also through the emotional connections that are successfully—or unsuccessfully—formed with global publics.

Communicative weaknesses are further intensified by the growing gap between message and perception. Gallarotti (2016, 2022a, 2022b) argues that soft power is often romanticised as a benign and peaceful form of influence, while in practice it may also possess a “dark side,” in which admiration is instrumentalised for illiberal or narrowly geopolitical purposes. In the case of BRICS, for example, dominant narratives tend to communicate economic strength and strategic positioning rather than shared normative values, thereby weakening the credibility and persuasive force of the message.

Rothman (2011) further notes that the literature lacks clear mechanisms explaining how admiration is translated into concrete political or behavioural outcomes, rendering soft power closer to a rhetorical label than to a rigorous communicative instrument. Scholars also emphasise the vulnerability of soft power to counter-discourses and negative narratives. Marlin-Bennett (2022) demonstrates that soft power can be appropriated for propaganda and disinformation, while Ellwood (2023) and Kern (2022) show that discrepancies between political rhetoric and actual behaviour rapidly erode international credibility. Bakalov (2019) adds that soft power is embedded with normative biases, which complicate communication with culturally diverse audiences and limit its universal appeal.

From the perspective of international relations, Henne (2022) critically examines the sources of soft power, emphasizing that culture—the first identified source—remains conceptually ambiguous with regard to its capacity to act as a form of power and influence external publics, particularly given that power is fundamentally a relational concept between states rather than a resource inherent to a state. Moreover, Henne (2022, p. 100) highlights that it is insufficiently explained how a state can deploy culture and ideology as instruments of power, and how these relate to material

resources, such as economic or military capabilities associated with hard power. The mere popularity or renown of a culture does not automatically translate into soft power. Similarly, the second category of soft power—political values—can also be contested, as Henne (2022) notes, because it is ultimately the subjective perceptions of the international community, rather than the mere presence of values, that shape influence. In other words, Nye's conception of 'political value' remains conceptually underdefined and requires analysis within its social and historical context. Even the third category—morally grounded foreign policy, or policies deemed 'good' by one state or culture—may be interpreted elsewhere as domination, intervention, or imperialism, illustrating the context-dependent and contested nature of soft power.

Taken together, these critiques suggest that while soft power remains relevant as a communicative tool, it is inherently fragile and deeply problematic. Its conceptual ambiguity, difficulties of measurement, neglect of emotional dynamics, exposure to reputational damage, and susceptibility to negative narratives render it an unstable form of influence. As Durrani's (2023) analysis indicates, soft power should be understood not only in terms of the accumulation of attractiveness, but also through the management of its erosion and loss, thereby placing strategic communication, reputation, and narratives at the centre of contemporary analysis.

4.3. A radically transformed communication environment

Nye explains soft power in a relatively basic manner—as attractive power—and situates it primarily within the field of international relations (Rothman, 2010). However, soft power without the promotion of values through public diplomacy remains ineffective. Communication tools such as media, exchange programs, and cultural diplomacy therefore constitute central mechanisms, as soft power operates at the intersection of communication and international relations (Hayden, 2017). Foreign audiences come to know a country's soft power through media exposure, visits, and local intermediaries—in other words, through people. Although Nye closely links soft power to international relations and acknowledges the importance of value exposure, he does not sufficiently engage with communication theory, public relations, or strategic communication. The promotion of values through public diplomacy is, in essence, a dialogical form of communication (Di Martino, 2019), and the core objective of public diplomacy is relationship-building through communication (Cull, 2010; Zaharna, 2014).

Today, this communication unfolds in a networked world (Castells, 2009), where global populations interact directly across multiple platforms (Van Dijck & De Waal, 2018), and where the hyperhistory of 4.5 billion people is continuously produced and circulated (Floridi, 2014). This environment differs fundamentally from the one described by Nye, which was characterised by monopolised media systems and television dominance. At that time, American public diplomacy relied heavily on outlets such as Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty targeting Eastern Europe, as well as Voice of America (VOA), Radio Martí, and Radio Sawa, which broadcast in multiple languages and delivered carefully managed messages to influence foreign audiences (Zaharna, 2010; Tuch, 1990; Szondi, 2008).

Soft power can be attractive only when it is known—that is, when it is communicated. In this sense, it becomes narrative power (Winkler, 2019). Yet narrative power has undergone profound transformation. Today, numerous non-state actors disseminate

their own narratives online. Nye himself acknowledges that the rise of digital communication has altered the conditions of soft power, which now faces intense competition from billions of online communicators and non-state actors, including corporations, non-profits, criminal networks, terrorist groups, and informal ad hoc collectives. Some of these actors are able to compete effectively with states in shaping global perceptions (Nye, 2019).

Nye also expresses concern about the credibility of value promotion in the cyber age. He argues that effective public diplomacy requires attention to credibility, self-criticism, and the role of civil society in generating soft power (Nye, 2019). At the same time, the use of new cyber technologies by authoritarian states to disrupt democratic processes raises critical questions about the limits of soft power and the appropriate strategies of contemporary public diplomacy (Nye, 2019).

The new public diplomacy is thus characterised by a broader and more inclusive understanding of its agents, channels, and publics (Spry, 2018). These agents and channels often circulate messages that resemble propaganda, driven by what has been described as the “colonisation of the media by PR” (Moloney & McGrath, 2020, p. 81), particularly in the context of “Facebook democracy” (Marichal, 2012).

These transformations in communication further complicate the identification of soft power sources, as today’s communicative actors include virtually the entire public—many of whom are not oriented toward promoting national values in the manner originally envisioned by Nye. Contemporary communication has shifted from top-down media structures to decentralised and participatory platforms, within which non-state actors play an increasingly significant role in shaping global narratives.

4.4. The institutionalisation of soft power and Nye’s paradox

Despite the criticisms and gaps identified by scholars in both the first and second decades of this century, the concept of soft power remains widely used by both academics and in public discourse, often as a fad. One reason for this widespread, fad-like usage is that the concept is associated with a Harvard professor, or, in other words, institutionalised through its link to a prestigious university. As Kuhn (1996) observes, theories can survive even when they enter a period of crisis, particularly when they are supported by prestigious institutions. This institutional backing has created a form of “epistemic shield,” through which the concept is protected and reproduced despite extensive criticism (Winkler, 2019). This dynamic is evident in the way many authors introduce the concept by emphasizing Nye’s institutional affiliation: “coined by Harvard political scientist Joseph Nye in 1990” (Cull, 2010; Ang et al., 2015); “the concept has been coined by Harvard professor Joseph Nye” (Wang & Stenberg, 2019; Winkler, 2019; Bakalov, 2019); or “the term soft power was made famous by the Harvard professor” (George, 2016; Parmar & Cox, 2010; Winkler, 2019).

The paradox is further intensified by Nye’s shifting positions regarding authorship. In some instances, he explicitly acknowledges that he coined the term (Nye, 2004), while in others he rejects this claim (Nye, 2021). This ambiguity of authorship mirrors the broader conceptual ambiguity that has accompanied soft power from its inception: is it a theory, a metaphor, or a normative framework for policymaking? As Fan (2007), Rothman (2011), and Bakalov (2019) argue, this lack of conceptual clarity has contributed to the transformation of soft power into an academic buzzword—widely used, yet weakly operationalised.

Within this context, Mowlana (2021), a prominent scholar of public diplomacy, emphasises that the idea underlying soft power is far older than contemporary literature suggests. He traces its roots back to antiquity and refers to the 13th century, when the Iranian author Golestan wrote: “When you see aggression, use softness, nothing matches the soft power”. Mowlana (2021) further notes that he himself used the term “intangible power” as early as 1978, whereas Nye later employed the term soft power to describe the same phenomenon (p. 3).

4.5. From soft power to strategic alliances

Even Nye (2021) himself acknowledges that concepts emerge within specific historical contexts and that these contexts evolve over time. Soft power functioned most effectively during a period when value differences between the West and the East were deep, visible, and politically salient. In contrast, the contemporary global environment is characterised by multipolarity, regional competition, and normative fragmentation (Manor & Golan, 2020). Under these conditions, international relations are increasingly shaped by pragmatic interests and strategic alignments rather than by ideological attraction.

Empirical developments suggest that states today do not necessarily align with the most ‘attractive’ actors, but rather with those that provide tangible security guarantees, economic benefits, or strategic advantages. In this context, soft power loses much of its explanatory capacity, giving way to the logic of flexible and often temporary alliances (Manor & Golan, 2020). This shift does not imply that communication has become irrelevant; rather, it indicates that communication no longer functions as a universal or autonomous tool of influence within the global system. This is particularly evident in the case of U.S. President Trump’s actions, when Britain cooled its relations with China and signed economic cooperation agreements (Tewari, 2026), while the EU and India concluded free trade agreements (Acharya, 2026). Actors who once shared common soft power values have become divided, and new alliances have emerged with those perceived as not sharing these values.

4.6. Dialogic engagement as a fundamental shortcoming of soft power

The values of soft power are disseminated among foreign publics primarily through public diplomacy activities (Nye, 2004). Public diplomacy aims to promote a given country and advance its foreign policy objectives by engaging and influencing foreign publics (Melissen, 2005; Tuch, 1990; Malone, 1985). In this respect, one of the most significant weaknesses of soft power lies in its insufficient conceptualisation of engagement. While communication scholarship defines engagement as a dialogic, cognitive, emotional, and behavioural process (Taylor & Kent, 2014; Dessart & Pitardi, 2019), soft power largely remains grounded in a one-directional model of value exposure. Nye emphasises admiration and attraction but gives little attention to interaction or to the co-creation of meaning between actors and audiences.

Contemporary publics increasingly engage with official narratives in active and reflexive ways, frequently contesting, reinterpreting, or subverting them altogether (Kim, 2021). In the absence of sustained dialogic engagement, soft power is therefore unlikely to generate durable relational influence, instead producing effects that are largely superficial or transient. Although communication scholarship identifies storytelling as a key mechanism for cultivating engagement and affective resonance

(Dessart & Pitardi, 2019; Qu & Saffer, 2023), this dimension remains insufficiently theorised in Nye's formulation of soft power, thereby constraining its analytical and explanatory utility in contemporary communicative environments.

Moreover, shifting global perceptions and communicative dynamics have further diminished the effectiveness of soft power as an instrument of state influence. In an increasingly networked and decentralised information ecosystem, where billions of individuals communicate directly across digital platforms (Van Dijck & De Waal, 2018; Floridi, 2014), states no longer possess the capacity to unilaterally shape or control the interpretation of their values. Consequently, traditional soft power instruments such as academic exchanges and student scholarship programs—once central to cultivating long-term international affinity—exert a more limited influence in the context of rapidly circulating and competing online narratives (Winkler, 2019; Saliu, 2022a).

Another dimension of soft power relevant for engaging foreign audiences is religion. Nye (2004) briefly references religion as a source of soft power when noting the global influence of the Vatican, recalling Stalin's ironic remark: 'How many divisions does the Pope have?' (p. 9). Henne (2022), however, argues that religion can play a significant role in shaping influence, using Russia as an example of Orthodox Christianity and Saudi Arabia as an example of Islam. The role of religion as a source of soft power is also explored extensively in the volume edited by Mandaville (2023), which examines how various states employ religion within their foreign policy strategies. These analyses collectively demonstrate how the concept of soft power can be expanded to address previously underexplored dimensions.

4.7. From political values to narrative power

However, not only in the case of religious values, but also with respect to other values encompassed by soft power, the majority of citizens worldwide obtain information about other countries primarily through the media rather than through activities managed by a state's public diplomacy strategists (Golan et al., 2019). Information and narratives play a central role in foreign communication and foreign policy (Krebs, 2015). For some countries, such narratives may be positive and romanticised, while for others they can be highly negative, with political elites, media, and cultural actors playing a significant role in their construction and dissemination (Spencer, 2016). The production of narratives in the public sphere is not limited to political actors such as state representatives, government officials, and political leaders; it also involves social activists, academics, experts, media professionals, and artists (Miskimmon et al., 2013). These actors make strategic choices about which narratives to deploy in order to shape broader discursive environments, thereby influencing the behaviour of others in both domestic and international politics in pursuit of their political objectives (Barthwal-Datta et al., 2023).

As Durrani (2023) demonstrates, visual and media narratives can just as easily generate losses of soft power through negative imagery, stereotyping, and processes of "othering". This shift moves the analytical focus away from the accumulation of attractiveness and toward the management of reputation and the prevention of narrative erosion. Increasingly, adversarial actors exploit narrative gaps through digital platforms and targeted campaigns designed to undermine the soft power of others (Pamment, 2023).

Soft power is premised on the assumption that certain political values are universally attractive. While this assumption was understandable in the geopolitical context of the 1990s, it has become deeply problematic in the contemporary global environment. Values are not fixed or universal; they are dynamic, contextual, and subject to negotiation and reinterpretation (Guth & Marsh, 2017; Smith, 2021; Saliu, 2025). What is perceived as a positive value in one context may be interpreted as imposition, inconsistency, or even hypocrisy in another. The neglect of emotional responses, cultural differences, and media biases often results in a misalignment between strategic intent and audience perception (Haugaard, 2019; Durrani, 2023).

In the era of social media and digital platforms, soft power—originally developed in the context of the Cold War—appears increasingly outdated. It struggles to account for a radically transformed communicative environment in which values once considered exclusive have become widespread, and where the main actors of influence are dispersed across a global online public that generates and circulates competing narratives beyond state control (Floridi, 2014; Krebs, 2015; Saliu, 2018, 2022b). Often, these narratives, disseminated by both populist politicians and billions of communication actors in the contemporary technological environment, undermine even the core values of a country's soft power.

4.8. From attractiveness to irrelevance

In a global environment where many states formally endorse similar political values and where information circulates freely and instantaneously, soft power loses its exclusivity. Democracy, human rights, and individual freedoms no longer function as clear markers distinguishing the “haves” from the “have-nots.” As a result, soft power loses its differentiating capacity and becomes an increasingly abstract concept that is difficult to operationalise empirically (Zhang & Wu, 2019).

In this sense, soft power is not merely weakened; it is theoretically surpassed. This is not because communication has lost its importance, but because the way Nye conceptualised the relationship between values, communication, and influence no longer corresponds to contemporary realities. Communication today is not linear, centralised, or state-controlled, but networked, contested, and shaped by multiple actors operating across diverse platforms.

In summary, the crisis of soft power is driven not only by geopolitical transformations, but more fundamentally by the profound restructuring of the communicative environment. Soft power remains anchored in a linear, state-centric, and value-based logic, whereas the contemporary world operates through networked narratives, plural actors, and dialogic engagement. This mismatch significantly reduces the concept's ability to explain or guide current practices of international influence.

From this perspective, the central question is no longer how soft power can be strengthened, but whether it continues to offer a valid analytical framework for understanding power in the age of globally distributed narratives.

5. Conclusions

There are several reasons today to reconsider the values and sources of soft power in light of the context in which Nye originally formulated the concept, namely the circumstances surrounding the end of the Cold War.

The first and most important reason is that the core values of soft power—values that non-democratic countries in Eastern Europe once lacked—such as good governance, democracy, justice, welfare, human rights, individual opportunity, culture, quality education, and a moral foreign policy, have now largely been achieved. Having already acquired these values, they are no longer as attractive to these countries as was assumed at the time Nye identified them as key sources of soft power. In some contexts, political and democratic values that were once highly esteemed have weakened under populist governments, while religious values have gained greater prominence than they held when the concept of soft power was first articulated.

Western countries that once shared—and in some cases still share—the same soft power values, and for which these values constituted a condition for good relations, are now increasingly engaging in pragmatic interactions that extend beyond such principles. As a result of populism, in some contexts soft power values no longer function as unifying elements in the way they once did. Hard power is increasingly asserted at the expense of soft power, and conflicts now emerge even among states that previously shared similar normative foundations. At the same time, states traditionally associated with soft power are moving beyond these values and forming strategic and economic alliances with actors that do not share the same Western democratic principles, but with whom they share strong economic and geostrategic interests more closely aligned with hard power considerations.

The actors and channels of communication have also changed, multiplied, and the communication environment has been fundamentally transformed. According to Nye, communication actors were once primarily state actors that promoted distinctive soft power values to target audiences. Today, the gap between the soft power sources of Western countries and those of formerly non-democratic states is no longer as pronounced, and, as a result, Western attractiveness has diminished. Communication actors also included academic and student exchanges, whose participants returned to their home countries expressing admiration for Western democratic values. This dynamic no longer operates in the same way in the European context.

Mass communication channels were once dominated by traditional media, whose messages addressed to external audiences were carefully managed. Today, however, the multiplication of media platforms has made it increasingly difficult to control or coordinate messages directed at foreign audiences. More importantly, the communication environment itself has been fundamentally transformed. Whereas in the past state actors conveyed messages to foreign audiences and non-state actors primarily benefited from exchange programs, today billions of individuals have become communicative actors who interact directly with foreign audiences in an independent and largely unmediated manner. They communicate their own culture, preferences, and attitudes without contributing to a coordinated or managed presentation of a country's soft power values. This development indicates that media and political actors have lost their monopoly over information and messaging directed at foreign audiences. In the global online sphere, communication is multidirectional

and continuous, and every individual with a social media account effectively functions as a medium in their own right.

Moreover, soft power has traditionally represented more elite values than popular ones, as Nye emphasised their universal character. In today's global platform society, however, communication is dominated by the majority of the population, many of whom have migrated online or are digital natives. Since most individuals—both within societies and globally—possess only an average level of cultural and intellectual formation, online discussions tend to reflect this general level of preferences and understanding. Widely used social media platforms clearly illustrate this tendency. As a result, average perceptions increasingly dominate global discourse, overshadowing the elite values traditionally associated with soft power. The individual narratives and stories of millions of online users often eclipse the managed strategies of state actors aimed at promoting soft power, frequently polarizing the online environment and, in doing so, undermining the core values that countries seek to project.

In other words, from the communicative perspective adopted in this study, it can be concluded that soft power values have shifted within the new geopolitical context, while communicative actors have also been transformed. Message senders are no longer primarily state or elite actors but billions of individuals who share their own preferences, attitudes, and narratives rather than those of the countries they nominally represent. Communication has become democratised, meaning that online message production is dominated not by elites but by the (often mediocre) majority of the population. In this environment, the credibility of information has declined, online disinformation has proliferated, and polarisation has intensified. Consequently, online commentators tend to reinforce the trajectories of populist leaders rather than the integrative principles traditionally associated with soft power.

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